

CONDUCTIVE POLYTHIOPHENE/POLYMER COMPOSITES AS ELECTROACTIVE MATERIAL APPLICATION

D. Pattavarakorn*, K. Jaitang, P. Kumchaiya, P. Chaimongkol and S. Thongbor
Department of Industrial Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Chiang Mai University,
Chiangmai, Thailand

* Corresponding author (dchpatt@gmail.com, cdatchan@chiangmai.ac.th)

Keywords: Electromechanical, Electrorheology, Conductive polymer, Polythiophene, PDMS, PVA, Composite

1 General Introduction

Electroactive polymers (EAPs) are polymer materials that change their shape or size in response to electrical stimuli. This class of materials is therefore a good candidate for actuators in the field of medical devices, soft manipulators and biomimetics, since they mimic the behavior of biological muscles [1]. The actuators have been produced for many sizes to a variety of styles application. Various materials have been made as actuator: sharp memory alloys (SMA) and electroactive ceramics [2]. However, these materials have limit in terms of weight and ability to change size or sharp. Dielectric elastomers are a type of electric-field-activated electroactive polymers that are capable of producing large strains, fast response, and high efficiency. Poly (dimethylsiloxane) [PDMS], an elastomer, is a potential candidate material for various actuator applications. It has excellent dielectric Properties and flexibility [3]. Currently, conductive polymer (CPs) is alternative to produce for actuators instead of a metallic material. The conductive polymers have many advantages over other material such as low cost, relatively simple fabrication, light weight and combine the mechanical properties (flexibility, toughness, elasticity, malleability, etc.) of plastics with high electrical conductivities [4], [5]. Many conductive polymers such as polyacetylene, polythiophene, polypyrrole, polyaniline have attracted much attention for their promising applications such as sensors, electrochemical displays, batteries, antistatic coatings, anticorrosive coatings, actuator, artificial muscles, functional membranes and controlled release of ionic drugs, etc. [6].

In this study, we are interested to develop polythiophene/polymers composites toward electroactive material application. The electromechanical properties; electrorheological properties and bending response under electric field are investigated in terms of polymer matrix type, polythiophene fraction and electric field strength.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

Thiophene (Fluka) was used as the monomer. Iron (III) chloride anhydrous, (Acros organics and Ajax Finechem) was used as the oxidant. Chloroform, (labscan Asia) and methanol (J.T. baker) were used as recieved. Hydroxyl terminated poly(dimethylsiloxane) (PDMS, viscosity 3,500 cSt, Aldrich), poly(vinyl alcohol) (PVA, Aldrich) and chitosan (CS, Ta Ming Enterprises) were used as matrixes. Tetraethyl orthosilicate (TEOS, Aldrich), glutaraldehyde (GA, Aldrich) and dibutyltin dilaurate (2EHSn, Aldrich) were used as crosslinking agents and a catalyst, respectively.

2.2 Synthesis of polythiophene (PTh)

Polythiophene was synthesized via chemical oxidative polymerization [7]. 145 g of FeCl₃ anhydrous was added to 800 ml of chloroform and the mixture was stirred in a 3-necked round bottom flask and heat at 40 °C with silicon oil basin. 24.60 g of thiophene monomer (C₄H₂S) was added to 100 ml of chloroform in a separatory funnel. The thiophene monomer solution was added dropwise to the FeCl₃ anhydrous solution with continuous stirring at room temperature for 3 hours. After all the thiophene monomer solution was added, the reaction

mixture was continuously stirred at 40 °C for 9.5 hours and the reaction mixture temperature was decreased to room temperature. After that, 800 ml of methanol was added to the reaction mixture and stirred for 1.5 hour in order to stop the reaction. Polythiophene particles were filtered using Buchner suction funnel and dried in vacuum oven at 27 °C for 24 hours.

2.3 Preparation of PTh/PDMS and PTh/PVA composite films

PTh/PDMS composite films were prepared according to the method of Haimtup et.al. [8]. PTh particles were mixed with PDMS and TEOS at a crosslinking agent to monomer ratio (C/M) of 0.053 and using 2EHSn as the catalyst. The mixture was poured in a mold and allowed to cure under vacuum for 24 hours. The PTh/PVA composite films were prepared followed Ezequiel et. al. [22 prawit]. The PTh particles were mixed with PVA/CS solution (weight ratio of PVA:CS equal to 75:25) and GA was then added as crosslinking agent.

2.4 Electromechanical properties measurement

The electromechanical properties of conductive composites were investigated in the way of electrorheological test and bending response test under the electric field. The effects of polythiophene particle concentration and electric field strength were studied. For the electrorheological properties study, composite samples with a diameter of 25 mm and a thickness of 1 mm were prepared. The sample was placed between parallel plates (diameter of 25 mm) of a modified melt rheometer (ARES, Rheometric Scientific Inc.) which is attached to a DC power supply. The samples were first checked for viscoelastic linearity by strain sweep tests. Experiments were carried out in the frequency sweep mode ranging from 0.1 to 100 rad/s to investigate the effect of electric field strength on the storage and loss moduli, G' and G'' . All experiments at each applied field strength were repeated twice to confirm reproducibility.

Finally, the bending response of the conductive composites in an electric field was investigated using the experimental set-up as shown in Fig. 1. The composite films were immersed vertically in a silicon oil (viscosity=100 cSt) bath, with a dc electric field applied horizontally between two parallel flat copper electrodes. DC electric field was applied with various strengths in the range of 0-700

V/mm. The amount of deflection at a specified field strength is defined by the geometrical parameters A, B and θ . The bend angle (θ) was calculated from the following equation,

$$\theta = \arctan (A/B) \quad (1)$$

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Characterization of polythiophene

The synthesized polythiophene was characterized by FTIR and UV-VIS spectrometry. It was found that polythiophene shows characteristic FTIR peaks at 787 cm^{-1} , 1219 cm^{-1} , 1367 cm^{-1} and 1736 cm^{-1} corresponding to the C-C bending vibration, C-C stretching vibration of α -coupled, C-H stretching vibration and C=C stretching vibration of the thiophene ring, respectively. The UV-Vis absorption spectrum of synthesized polythiophene in DMF solution shows absorption peak at 375 nm and 321 nm. Fig. 2 shows the scanning electron microscopy of synthesized polythiophene particles. It can be seen that the shapes of the polythiophene particles and their surfaces are quite irregular. In addition, the specific conductivity of synthesized polythiophene was measured using the two-point probe meter. It was found that the specific conductivity of polythiophene equal to 8.97×10^{-5} S/cm.

3.2 Electrorheological properties of the composites

The effects of polymer matrix, particle concentration and electric field strength on electrorheological properties of the composites were explored. Particle volume fraction investigated was varied from 0 to 30 vol. % and the electric field strength was varied as 0-2 kV/mm. The magnitude of the response is characterized as the difference in storage modulus with the field on (G'_E) and off (G'_{E_0}), $\Delta G' = G'_E - G'_{E_0}$, of the composites.

3.2.1 Effect of particle concentration

Fig. 3 shows the modulus response of the composites as a function of polythiophene particle concentration. It was found that the modulus responses of the PTh/PDMS composite much greater than the PTh/PVA composite. This might because of higher rigidity of PVA matrix than PDMS. Moreover, the composites with a higher volume

fraction show better storage modulus response because of stronger electrostatic interactions, since the average distance between particles is smaller, and these forces increase strongly as the interparticle spacing decreases [10].

3.2.2 Effect of electric field strength

Fig. 4 shows the storage modulus response of the composites as a function of electric field strength. It can be seen that the response of each system generally increases with increasing electric field strength. As an electric field is increased, both polythiophene particles and polymer matrix become more polarize, leading to higher dipole moment and intermolecular interactions.

3.3 Bending response of the composites

The bending response or deflection of PTh/PDMS and PTh/PVA composites under electric field was investigated. Fig. 5 and Fig. 6 show images of the bending of PTh/PDMS and PTh/PVA composites respectively, immersed in silicone oil at different electric field strengths. The figures show that on applying the electric field, the free lower end of the composite bends towards the anode by an amount dependent on the field strength. It is indicating an attractive interaction between the applied field and the polarized polythiophene particles in the composites.

3.3.1 Effect of particle concentration

The bending angle as a function of polythiophene particle concentration at the field strength of 0.7 kV/mm is shown in Fig. 7. The composites have higher bending angle when the particle concentration increased. The PTh/PDMS and PTh/PVA composites with 10 vol.% polythiophene show maximum bending angle of 22.01° and 10.61° , respectively. The increase in bending angle of composites can be attributed to the increase of induced polarization which leading to the increase of interactions between polythiophene particles in polymer matrix and copper electrode.

3.3.2 Effect of electric field strength

Fig. 8 shows the bending angle vs. electric field strength of the 10 vol.% polythiophene composites. It can be seen that the bending angle response appears to increase with increasing of electric field strength, according to greater polarization of

polythiophene particles which lead to higher interaction between polythiophene particle and polymer matrix.

4 Conclusions

In this study, the electromechanical properties; electrorheological properties and bending response of polythiophene/poly (dimethyl siloxane), PTh/PDMS and polythiophene/polyvinyl alcohol, PTh/PVA composites were investigated by examining the effects of polythiophene particle concentration and electric field strength varying from 0 to 2 kV/mm. The storage modulus response ($\Delta G'$) increases with particle concentration and electric field strength due to polythiophene particles and poly(dimethyl siloxane) molecules become more polarized by electric field, leading to higher attraction between the induced electric dipoles on the polythiophene particles and also higher intermolecular interaction between polythiophene particles and polymer. For the bending response, PTh/PDMS system has better response than pure PDMS in which higher bending angle can be observed. In addition, the bending angle seems to be increased with increasing polythiophene volume fraction and electric field strength.

5 Acknowledgments

The authors wish to thanks Prof. Anuvat Sirivat, the Conductive and Electroactive Polymers Research Unit, the Petroleum and Petrochemical College for the assistance of testing equipment and we would like to acknowledge the financial support provided by the Thailand Research Fund (TRF-MRG5380100).

Fig.1. Schematic diagram of the apparatus used to observe the bending response [8].

Fig.2. The morphology of polythiophene particles.

Fig. 3. Storage modulus response of the composite with various particle concentrations at electric field strength of 2.0 kV/mm.

Fig. 4. Storage modulus response of the 10 %vol. polythiophene composite at various applied voltages.

Fig. 5. Bending response of the PTh/PDMS at various applied voltages.

Fig. 6. Bending response of the PTh/PVA at various applied voltages.

Fig.7. Bending angle of composites with various particle concentrations at electric field strength of 0.7 kV/mm.

Fig. 8. Bending angle of 10% polythiophene composites at various electric field strengths.

References

- [1] D. Brandell, H. Kasemagi and A. Aabloo "Poly(ethylene oxide)-poly(butadiene) interpenetrated networks as electroactive polymers for actuators: A molecular dynamics study". *Electrochimica Acta*, Vol. 55, No. 4, pp 1333-1337, 2010.
- [2] P. Thipdech, R. Kunanuruksapong and A. Sirivat "Electromechanical responses of poly(3-thiopheneacetic acid)/acrylonitrile-butadiene rubbers". *Express polymer letter*, Vol. 2, No. 12, pp 866-877, 2008.
- [3] W. Wichiansee and A. Sirivat "Electrorheological properties of poly(dimethylsiloxane) and poly(3,4-ethylenedioxy thiophene)/poly(styrene sulfonic acid)/ethylene glycol blends". *Materials Science and Engineering C*, Vol. 29, No. 1, pp 78-84, 2009.
- [4] C. Chuapradit, L. Wannatong, D. Chotpattananont, P. Hiamtup, A. Sirivat and J. Schwank "Polyaniline/zeolite LTA composites and electrical conductivity response toward CO". *Polymer*, Vol. 46, No. 3, pp 947-953, 2005.
- [5] G.G. Wallace, G.M. Spinks, L. Kane-Maguire and P.R. Teasdale "*Conductive Electroactive Polymers: Intelligent Materials Systems*". 2nd edition, CRC Press, 2003.
- [6] D. Zhou, S. Subramaniam and J.E. Mark "In situ Synthesis of Polyaniline in Poly(dimethylsiloxane) Networks Using an Inverse Emulsion Route". *Journal of Macromolecular Science, Part A: Pure and Applied Chemistry*, Vol. 42, No. 2, pp 113-126, 2005.
- [7] K.S. Ryu, Y. Lee, K.S. Han and M.G. Kim "The electrochemical performance of polythiophene synthesized by chemical method as the polymer battery electrode". *Materials chemistry and physics*, Vol. 84, No. 2-3, pp 380-384, 2004.
- [8] P. Hiamtup, A. Sirivat and A.M. Jamieson "Electromechanical response of a soft and flexible actuator based on polyaniline particles embedded in a cross-linked poly(dimethyl siloxane) network". *Materials science and engineering C*, Vol. 28, No. 7, pp 1044-1051, 2008.
- [9] E.S. Costa-Junior, E.F. Barbosa, A.P. Mansar, W.L. Vanconcelos and H.S. Mansur "Preparation and characterization of chitosan/poly(vinyl alcohol) chemically crosslinked blends for biomedical applications". *Carbohydrate Polymer*, Vol. 76, No. 3, pp 472-481, 2009.
- [10] R. Sakurai, H. See, T. Saito and M. Sumita "Effect of matrix viscoelasticity on the electrorheological properties of particle suspensions". *J. Non-Newton. Fluid Mech.*, Vol. 81, pp 235-250, 1999.